

DISSOCIATION PRESSURES AND PRESSURE-COMPOSITION ISOTHERMALS OF COPPER PYRIDINE NITRATES

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The dissociation pressures of the pyridine complexes of copper nitrate have been measured at different temperatures and the isothermal curves showing pressures against number of molecules of pyridine per molecule of copper nitrate have been determined at 30°. From these results it has been proved that in the solid phase three complexes, namely $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6 \text{py}$, $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 5 \text{py}$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 4 \text{py}$ are formed. The heats of dissociation of the three complexes have been calculated by the help of Clapeyron-Clausius equation and the linear graphs $-\log_{10} p$ against $10^3/T$; and their values correspond to 8,950 cal, 13,420 cal and 14,350 cal respectively showing that the 4-pyridine complex is the most stable and the 6-pyridine complex, the least so.

By measurement of dissociation pressures of copper pyridine perchlorates at different temperatures and study of pressure-composition isothermals of copper perchlorate-pyridine system at 30° and 50°, Sinha and Ray (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1948, 44, 790) have proved that in the solid phase only two stable complexes, viz., $\text{Cu}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 6 \text{py}$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 4 \text{py}$ are formed. From determination of the partition coefficient of copper perchlorate between water and pyridine, the same authors (this *Journal*, 1948, 25, 247) have shown that the two complexes $\text{Cu}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 4 \text{py}$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 6 \text{py}$ are present in aqueous solutions. The present investigation was undertaken with a view to ascertaining the influence, if any, of the anion on the composition and stability of the complexes formed under similar conditions. The nitrate ion being much smaller in size than the perchlorate ion was therefore selected for the study. The dissociation pressures of copper pyridine nitrates have been measured at different temperatures, and the number of copper pyridine nitrates, which are definitely formed under laboratory conditions, has also been determined by an isothermal study of the copper nitrate-pyridine system at 30°. In the present case indication of the formation of four complexes has been obtained. The complex which contains the highest amount of pyridine approximates to $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 7 \text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N}$, but as the dissociation pressures of this complex with temperature are not reproducible, it appears that it is not a stable compound, but it is formed by adsorption, and is therefore left out. The other three complexes, namely, $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6 \text{py}$, $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 5 \text{py}$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 4 \text{py}$, which give reversible and reproducible dissociation pressures, must be regarded as definite compounds. It will be noticed that the complexes of pyridine obtained with copper nitrate are similar to those which are formed with copper perchlorate, indicating that the anion has little or no influence in determining the nature and composition of the complexes formed.

EXPERIMENTAL

Copper nitrate-pyridine complex was prepared by the method of Grossmann (*Fer.*, 1904, 37, 1254) by treating a cold saturated solution of copper nitrate with excess of

pyridine, filtering the precipitated substance on a Buchner funnel and washing with pyridine.

The apparatus used for the determination of the dissociation pressures and the procedure followed have been described in a previous paper by Sinha and Ray (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1948, **44**, 790). The experiments were carried out in an air-thermostat, the temperature of which was controlled electrically and maintained constant to $\pm 0.1^\circ$. The substance was placed in a bulb which was sealed to a closed limbbed manometer. The thermostat was set to different temperatures and the pressures determined by reading the heights of mercury in the two limbs of the manometer by means of a cathetometer.

The results obtained are recorded in Table I and represented graphically in Fig. 1. The logarithms of pressures are also plotted against the reciprocals of the absolute temperature and the linear graphs thus obtained are shown in Fig. 2.

FIG. 1

The determination of isothermals consisted mainly of the measurements of the loss of weight of pyridine with its gradual removal at a fixed temperature. The loss of weight of the bulb containing the complex with progressive removal of pyridine was determined by weighing the bulb at intervals and the corresponding dissociation pressures were also measured. Thus a series of pressure values and the weights corresponding to each pressure were obtained. The apparatus used and the method of working

have been fully described in a previous paper (Sinha and Ray, *loc. cit.*). The results obtained are recorded in Table II and shown in Fig. 3 where the pressures are plotted against the number of molecules of pyridine per molecule of copper nitrate. The isothermals were determined at 35°. The determinations could not be made at higher temperatures because the compound began to decompose at 50°.

TABLE I

Temperature-pressure values.

System $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6/5$ py.				System $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 5/4$ py.				System $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 4/0$ py.			
Temp. (t°)	Pressure (mm. Hg.)	$\log_{10} p.$	$1/T \times 10^3.$	Temp. (t°)	Pressure (mm. Hg.)	$\log_{10} p.$	$1/T \times 10^3.$	Temp. (t°)	Pressure (mm. Hg.)	$\log_{10} p.$	$1/T \times 10^3.$
23	5.7	0.7559	3378	30	5.0	0.6990	3300	30	3.7	0.5682	3300
27	6.9	0.8423	3333	35	7.4	0.8692	3247	35	5.6	0.7482	3247
30	8.0	0.9031	3300	40	10.3	1.0128	3195	40.1	8.1	0.9085	3194
35	10.2	1.0102	3247	45	14.6	1.1644	3145	45	11.7	1.0682	3145
40	13.0	1.1139	3195	50	19.8	1.2967	3096	50	16.0	1.2041	3096
45	16.2	1.2101	3145								
50	20.2	1.3054	3096								
Mean value of the heat of dissociation (calc. from the graph), 8,950 cal.				Mean value of the heat of dissociation (calc. from the graph), 13,420 cal.				Mean value of the heat of dissociation (calc. from the graph), 14,350 cal.			

TABLE II

Pressure.	Loss in wt. of the bulb.	Loss in number of mols. of py per mol. of $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2.$	No. of mols. of py in the bulb per mol. of $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2.$	Pressure.	Loss in wt. of the bulb.	Loss in number of mols. of py per mol. of $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2.$	No. of mols. of py in the bulb per mol. of $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2.$
27 mm.	...	...	8.960	5/8 mm.	0.0280	0.205	4.314
"	0.1450 g.	1.059	7.900	"	0.0260	0.190	4.124
"	0.2400	1.754	6.14	"	0.0086	0.063	4.061
"	0.0158	0.115	6.032	3.7	0.0157	0.115	3.946
8 mm.	0.0176	0.129	5.903	"	0.0184	0.135	3.811
"	0.0131	0.096	5.807	"	0.0581	0.425	3.386
"	0.0143	0.105	5.702	"	0.0373	0.275	3.111
"	0.0132	0.096	5.606	"	0.0412	0.301	2.810
"	0.0159	0.116	5.490	"	0.0567	0.414	2.396
"	0.0201	0.147	5.343	"	0.0471	0.343	2.053
"	0.0430	0.314	5.029	"	0.0398	0.291	1.762
5 mm.	0.0480	0.351	4.678	"	0.0467	0.341	1.421
"	2.0218	0.159	4.519				

DISCUSSION

The results of measurements of the dissociation pressures at varying temperatures and the determination of pyridine molecules per molecule of copper nitrate isothermally at 30° leave no doubt that three stable complexes are formed, namely, $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{py}$, $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 5\text{py}$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 4\text{py}$. It must be mentioned, however, that vapour pressure measurements gave indication of the formation of a complex containing more than six molecules of pyridine attached to a molecule of copper nitrate. As these pressure values were not always reproducible, and especially as no break corresponding to this complex could be obtained in the isothermal studies, they were left out. It appears that loose adsorption compounds are formed. When the dissociating complex is in contact with an arbitrarily fixed concentration of pyridine vapour, it may be assumed that this is in equilibrium with the adsorbed pyridine molecules on the surface of finely divided and porous solid product and this equilibrium extends also to the reaction interface. A similar phenomenon was observed by Topley and Smith (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 321) in their study of the kinetics of salt hydrate dissociation: $\text{MnC}_2\text{O}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O} = \text{MnC}_2\text{O}_4 + 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

FIG. 2

The graphs obtained by plotting $\log_{10} p$ against $(1/T) \times 10^3$ are straight lines as shown in Fig. 2. The heats of formation of the three pyridine complexes can be calculated by the help of Clapeyron—Clausius equation and the slope of the linear

graphs of $\log_{10} p$ against $(1/T)$. The mean values of the heats of formation of the three complexes, $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{py}$, $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 5\text{py}$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 4\text{py}$, are thus found to be 8,950 cals., 13,420 cals. and 14,350 cals. respectively, showing that the 4-pyridine complex is the most stable and the 6-pyridine complex, the least so, while the stability of the 5-pyridine complex is intermediate between these two.

Dissociation pressures have been measured up to 50° . The measurements could not be carried out at higher temperatures on account of the oxidising action of the nitrate ions on pyridine with consequent decomposition of the compounds, and for this reason isothermal measurements could not be made at 50° or at higher temperatures. It has therefore not been possible to determine the transition temperatures of the complexes.

FIG. 3

It will be seen (Fig. 3) that the isothermal study shows three definite breaks corresponding to the three complexes, $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{py}$, $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 5\text{py}$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 4\text{py}$. In a previous paper Sinha and Ray (*loc. cit.*) showed that in the solid phase copper perchlorate formed with pyridine two stable complexes, namely $\text{Cu}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 6\text{py}$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{py}$ under similar conditions. It will thus be seen that the limits of the pyridine molecules which can combine with the copper salts are the same in the two cases, indicating that the nature and the size of the anion have little or no influence in the formation of the complexes.

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